

Decolonising Epistemic Injustice in Global Health

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Abstract

I critique of the use of “epistemic injustice” and “decolonisation” in global health. Fricker’s ethico-epistemic notion of epistemic injustice, which focuses on harms to knowers rather than the truth of claims, struggles to apply in empirical fields where error can have material health consequences. In global health, the usage tends to conflate moral recognition with epistemic warrant. It encourages the levelling of credibility across competing claims irrespective of evidence. I trace how decolonial and pluriversal rhetoric—drawing on Quijano, Grosfoguel, Mignolo, and Lugones—extends this conflation into ontological pluralism, dissolving truth into perspective while retaining universalist health ambitions. Through cases of spirit children, umbilical cord care, and snakebite treatment, I show how these frameworks can licence harmful practices and obscure structural analyses of power independent of coloniality. I conclude by sketching a modest alternative: epistemic humility, realist standards of evidence, and procedural justice in access to the means of inquiry.

Keywords: Decolonising; Epistemic injustice; Global Health

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Introduction

At the end of the century, the philosopher of science, Ian Hacking, wrote “The Social Construction of What?” [1] The book explored the rise in academic research claiming that something was “socially constructed”—disability, illness, crime, grief, and even personhood.

Hacking did not doubt that certain things are genuinely constructed through social, institutional, and scientific processes. Nor did he think that social construction meant that the categories are arbitrary or unreal. The categories have real effects and create feedback loops—the classifications themselves shape how people in those categories behave and perceive themselves, as well as how others interact with them.

However, others used “socially constructed” as a shorthand to claim that a category was arbitrary, oppressive, or could be wished away. This meaning was not Hacking’s point at all.

Hacking was interested in how something was constructed, recognising that construction has real effects, and acknowledging that constructed things can still be quite resistant to change. Nevertheless, the simplified version, declaring that X is constructed, therefore X is unjust, proved much more useful in the academic mainstream for signalling virtue than for advancing knowledge.

The adoption of this style of moral catchphrase has invaded global health and development in a different form. Today, to declare “epistemic injustice” or call for “decolonisation” in the title of an academic paper is to claim the moral high ground. It also forecloses debate because to dispute the claim is treated as an endorsement of injustice or support for colonialism. Few people have called “bullshit”. This essay is such a call.

I am not refuting that colonisation has caused harm, that coloniality can persist, or that (narrowly) harm may arise if people/groups with knowledge have that knowledge suppressed. The problem is that the terms have become flat, unnuanced cudgels that do not offer useful analytic lenses for the very things about which they claim concern. As with “social construction”, the power of “epistemic injustice” and “decolonisation” does not lie in analytic sharpness but in the rhetorical appeal of its moral message. They end up serving as markers of virtue rather than as critical tools for evaluation and assessment.

Epistemic injustice

The concept of epistemic injustice emerged in the early 2000s in analytic philosophy. The first significant work was Miranda Fricker’s “Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of Knowing” [2]. Fricker identifies two primary forms of epistemic injustice. First, there is what she calls “testimonial injustice”, whereby a speaker is denied credibility because of a prejudicial stereotype associated with a social or group characteristic. For example, a woman may be ignored or dismissed when offering mechanical advice due to embedded social hierarchies and traditional roles. Second, there is what Fricker calls “hermeneutical injustice”, whereby groups do not have the vocabulary and ways to think about and name a problem. The paradigmatic example is *sexual harassment (p.1)*. Until there were ways to think about sexual harassment in the workplace, talk about it, and name it, there was no mechanism to address it.

The concept has evolved considerably since Fricker first wrote about it. Contemporary scholars have extended epistemic injustice beyond failures to recognise individual knowers to include structural epistemic exclusion [3], intersecting axes of oppression [4], and collective or group-level harms [5]. Decolonial arguments, particularly in global health and development, have used the idea of epistemic injustice to critique how Western academic institutions systematically marginalise non-Western knowledge systems [6]. Feminist epistemologists have broadened the framework to analyse how entire communities are silenced or excluded from knowledge production [7]. However, the core notions—that epistemic wrongs attach to failures of credibility and interpretation—remain foundational, and the later structural and decolonial developments preserve the same conflation of moral recognition with epistemic warrant.

Correctly understood, epistemic injustice does not attend to the truth of propositions or to the allocation of effort to determine the truth of propositions. These things are precisely, however, the epistemic concerns that matter in global health and development—which interventions should we investigate first, and how do they work? Epistemic injustice is, thus, a moral category doing epistemic work, rather than a genuinely epistemic category. Fricker herself characterises epistemic injustice as an ethico-epistemic notion—a hybrid concept that combines ethical and epistemic evaluation within a single framework. For our purposes here, the description can be accepted. Whether the joint notion can withstand its first encounter with empirical inquiry and practice, however, requires careful consideration. Ethical and epistemic norms need to be kept distinct to preserve evidential integrity.

This need is apparent when one understands that epistemic injustice focuses on harms to knowers rather than harms to knowledge itself. Fricker defines epistemic injustice as wronging someone specifically in their capacity as a knower, through credibility deficits or hermeneutical marginalisation [2]. The framework centres on recognition of one's status as a knower, one's credibility, and one's interpretive resources—rather than on the epistemic warrant or truth-value of particular knowledge claims. In applications to global health and development, this emphasis on recognition extends to questions of whose knowledge gains visibility, whose expertise is credited, and who has access to platforms for knowledge dissemination [6]. In practice, this emphasis on recognition often blurs into competition for visibility, authorship, and funding, where claims of injustice become substitutes for epistemic warrant.

In global health and development, epistemic injustice is often claimed when a dominant group fails to recognise the *knowledge* of a non-dominant group. The unrecognised might be indigenous herbalists, local farmers, mothers, traditional birth attendants, and so forth. I put *knowledge* in italics not to disparage the knowledge but to identify that the truth of the proposition has not been evaluated and warranted by the dominant group according to their accepted methodological norms.

It is important, however, to distinguish epistemic injustice from epistemic harm. A person may suffer epistemic harm—such as misunderstanding, exclusion, or the loss of interpretive resources—without anyone committing a moral wrong. For example, a local herbalist's botanical insight might be lost because the translator lacks the necessary technical vocabulary. The loss is a communication failure, not an act of prejudice or malice. Fricker's framework, however, binds the two together: if there is an epistemic harm, there is also a moral wrong. In empirical fields such as global health and development, that conflation matters. Many epistemic harms are tragic but not unjust. The concept

can illuminate who is heard within expert settings, but it cannot determine what is true about the world.

An instructive example lies in the treatment of Indigenous oral histories. For generations, non-Indigenous scholars have dismissed these accounts as myths or folkloric. In Australia, geological and archaeological evidence has since confirmed that some describe real events, such as volcanic eruptions and ancient sea-level rise [8–10]. Their long dismissal reflected contempt rather than disbelief—a refusal to imagine that such testimony might hold truth. However, even here, it is unclear who, in any meaningful sense, was wronged or who did the wronging. Oral traditions are collective, anonymous, and intergenerational; disbelief arises diffusely through institutions and norms rather than through identifiable actors. The moral grammar of wrong and wronged thus begins to fail at precisely the point where the framework of epistemic injustice expects it to illuminate.

This difficulty arises partly from the post-Enlightenment impulse to assign attribution and establish priority [11]. In arguments about epistemic injustice, authors often conflate discovery with knowledge. In oral traditions, knowledge is not possessed but shared; its authority lies in continuity and diffusion, rather than in individuation. The framework of epistemic injustice, which depends on personal credibility and discrete moral agency, translates poorly to the composite and uneven bodies of knowledge sustained within oral traditions, where narrative wheat and chaff coexist—parts moral, parts epistemic, and parts technical.

The same distinction applies when authors raise claims of testimonial injustice. It may be true that the non-dominant group possesses knowledge (a justified true belief). Equally, the *knowledge* may be false—an error in understanding about the nature of the world. There is no legitimate moral claim, however, that a group is wronged simply because its false or untested beliefs are not recognised as knowledge. Dominant groups set priorities about which *knowledge* claims they will investigate—usually a series of experimental hypotheses proposed by members of the dominant group—and they possess the means to pursue them.

Whether the indigenous *knowledge* is knowledge remains unknown to the dominant group. We know of historical instances in which groups whose *knowledge* was unrecognised did, in fact, have profound and important insights. If the dominant group had recognised the knowledge, it might have improved lives, health, and wellbeing. An excellent example of this is knowledge about the benefits of variolation for the inoculation against smallpox. At the time, the dominant group chose to suppress variolation in favour of cowpox-based vaccination, even though variolation was at least as effective and in wide use [12].

We also know that there are groups whose *knowledge* was unrecognised and, if it had been recognised and influenced practice, it would have perpetuated significant harm. Furthermore, the dominant group's recognition of the knowledge may have even led to an expansion of the harmful practice. In Northern Ghana, members of a non-dominant group can identify that a newborn infant is a “spirit child”—a child who should never have been born [13]. An elder will recognise a spirit child by the restlessness in the cattle in the compound or the appearance of little footprints in the ash around the fire. The dominant group does not recognise this *knowledge*, and the infanticide associated with the identification of a spirit child is condemned. Placing cow dung on the umbilical cord stump of a newborn infant has not been recognised as knowledge by the dominant group, and

the dominant group goes so far as to assert knowledge that the practice causes neonatal tetanus [14,15]. The unwarranted recognition of *knowledge* about the value of cow dung on the umbilicus risks promoting harm, and claims of epistemic injustice cannot pre-empt or trump empirical assessment. Traditional treatments for snakebite offer a similar lesson. Multiple “knowers” propose contradictory remedies, some with plausible biochemical leads, but many cause delay, infection, or death, underscoring that moral recognition cannot replace empirical testing [16–18].

There are a multitude of these types of traditional *knowledge* from the practice of female genital mutilation [19] through to vaccine denial [20]. They are not exclusive to any part of the world and may arise everywhere, from Idaho in the Midwest of the United States to Lyon in France. Each denied group may have a sense of the injustice associated with others’ failure to recognise their *knowledge* as knowledge.

Fricker's framework faces a circularity problem when applied to fields like global health and development. The philosopher Julia Driver [21] has identified how moral and epistemic evaluation can be wrongly merged. Fricker's approach risks this by assessing belief-formation through criteria that conflate moral recognition with epistemic warrant. This problem extends in an acute manner to empirical and practice-based disciplines where consequences are real.

First, the framework presupposes criteria for identifying legitimate knowers and valid knowledge claims, but what are these criteria? Who decides which marginalised groups merit recognition? How large must the group of knowers be to have a claim? Is a group of one enough?

Second, applying the framework conflates two entirely different problems. Fricker’s paradigmatic example of sexual harassment exemplifies a hermeneutical problem—we lack the concept for identifying and addressing it. There is also an evidentiary problem—an empirical dispute about the truth-value of a proposition. Sexual harassment requires recognition and naming. The impact of dung on the umbilicus requires testing.

Third, the framework provides no mechanisms for distinguishing between unjust dismissal of true insights and justified rejection of false claims.

Finally, the framework assumes that power determines whose knowledge is heard, while simultaneously suggesting that marginalised perspectives offer an epistemic advantage. However, it provides no cogent way to decide between competing claims except by invoking the very power hierarchies it claims to critique. In short, the framework collapses standing-wrongs and evidentiary disputes, assumes what it must prove about who counts as a knower, and offers no internal means of distinguishing between true and false claims.

As it stands, a person/group is harmed in virtue of being unrecognised as knowers, even if they feel no harm. Furthermore, because the *knowledge* need not be true for epistemic injustice to have occurred, the framework strongly incentivises, in this context, a levelling of credibility for any claim, regardless of truth or method. In doing so, it risks collapsing epistemic standards into egalitarian sentiment. This collapse is a practical consequence of the framework’s internal logic, not an explicit prescription.

The consequence for global health and development is profound. The framework can generate and support genuine harms—such as death, injury, starvation, and physical mutilation—through a

requirement that “knowers” and, therefore, *knowledge* are treated as equal to and as valuable as knowledge, all in order to avoid a putative moral harm. I would previously have dismissed this line of argument as hyperbolic had I not heard an author of a global health paper on epistemic injustice roundly criticise the requirement that *knowledge* had to be true.

Nothing here denies the value of participatory research or the need to redress exploitation. It is to insist that the test of a claim about knowledge and truth in global health and development remains the same for all: evidence proportionate to the harm of error.

A community member is well-placed to speak about their lived experience, just as a blind person is uniquely placed to describe their perceptual world, or a person in chronic pain to describe their suffering. Nevertheless, these standpoints do not confer epistemic privilege beyond the domain of experience itself. Standpoint does not make one an authority on optics, hippopotami, or malaria. To confuse private experiential insight with evidentiary authority is to mistake first-person access for third-person expertise.

Lived experience confers narrative authority about what it is like for *that* person to inhabit a condition, and it can generate hypotheses about the wider world, sometimes generalising to others in similar circumstances. Whether those hypotheses are true—or whether the experience does generalise—is a separate, evidentiary matter. Marginal perspectives should broaden inquiry, not foreclose it.

This is the cardinal weakness of standpoint epistemology in its populist form: it slides from the uncontroversial claim that all knowers are situated to the indefensible claim that marginality itself yields superior insight. The move is rhetorically convenient—moral worth is taken as epistemic warrant—but it is incoherent. Standpoints reveal what it is like to live within a condition. They do not determine what is true of it. Lived experience may supply hypotheses or alert inquiry to neglected phenomena, but it cannot substitute for the evidential tests that convert experience into knowledge. This position also does not preclude a person with a standpoint view from being a domain expert and contributing valuable ideas from both their individual experience as a standpoint holder (first-person experience) and their domain expertise (third-person expertise).

Inquiry is selective rather than consultative. I am not obliged to listen to every claimant who asserts knowledge; nor would doing so serve justice. The obligation in research is to pursue questions with plausible causal traction, using scarce resources for the greatest epistemic and social yield.

True epistemic justice acknowledges that asymmetries of attention are not injustices when they track methodological competence and evidential promise. A refusal to entertain every claim is not exclusion; it is a matter of discipline. To conflate that discipline with oppression is to mistake the governance of knowledge for the governance of persons.

The 2021 article by Bhakuni and Abimbola, “Epistemic Injustice in Academic Global Health” [22], is a notable example of how Fricker’s concept was incorporated into global health discourse. Their work demonstrates the now-familiar extension of epistemic injustice from interpersonal ethics to structural critique, illustrating how, within global health, the concept has become closely entwined with decolonisation rhetoric. For Bhakuni and Abimbola, epistemic injustice functions less as an epistemological analysis than as a moral and political programme for the decolonisation of knowledge.

Decolonising Global Health

Many people working in global health view it as an activity that high-income countries undertake in low-income countries (the Global North in the Global South, the Developed World in the Developing World, the Minority World in the Majority World, or some similar configuration). This view is reflected in the semantic laundering used by European and North American universities as they transitioned from *colonial* or *international* health labels in the early to mid-twentieth century—which were distinctly about “doing health in”—to the current *global health* label. While the label changed, the research and training preserved the earlier dynamic: the Global North acting upon the communities and institutions of the Global South. The North-South geographic partition remains visible in the way European and North American international development assistance (aid) is dispersed under the rubric of global health.

A stark power dynamic evolved in health delivery, health research, and health systems. The money ostensibly flowed from North to South, while substantial benefits accrued to the Global North. Research conducted in the Global South has generated publications, citations, and career advancement opportunities for Northern researchers, benefiting their institutions and the Northern journals that publish their work. Data collection was frequently extractive, with intellectual property rights owned or managed in the Global North. Tied aid requirements, overhead financing structures, and capacity-building frameworks ensured that when money did flow South, Northern institutions captured value. Southern researchers often remained subordinate co-investigators in their own contexts. Moreover, when Global North experts structured health systems and designed service delivery, Global South communities became the subjects of interventions developed elsewhere, their autonomy secondary to external protocols, priorities and structures.

Frequently, although not always the case, the relationship between North and South is outrageous. The arguments that evolved to address the disparity (with a few exceptions [23]) centre on the notion of decolonising global health. Depending on who is making the call, it can mean anything from fair treatment to a complete revolution of ontology and epistemology. A recent scoping review of this literature also records this diversity, noting repeated invocations of epistemic injustice and calls for ontological pluralism within global health discourse [24].

The call to decolonise draws on a family of postcolonial thinkers who share a moral and political commitment to liberation and equality. Their accounts of knowledge are not developed as epistemologies in the strict sense, but rather emerge from their ethical and political projects. They differ, however, in how far they see that moral commitment dictates an understanding of knowledge and truth. At the realist end of the spectrum, Frantz Fanon [25] and Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak [26] both recognise that knowledge is patterned by power. Nonetheless, they maintain that truth remains independent of who holds it. For them, injustice lies in the obstruction of access to truth, not in the nature of truth itself. They would both concede that power shapes what is investigated and who is heard, but not what is true about the world.

Moving further towards relativist or antirealist positions, Aníbal Quijano [27,28] and Ramón Grosfoguel [29,30] argue that power not only shapes what is investigated but also conditions what can count as knowledge. They see modernity itself as a colonial project in which European ways of knowing define the terms of truth and exclude others. Knowledge, in this view, cannot be separated

from the structures of domination that sustain it. The test of a knowledge claim, therefore, becomes ethical as well as epistemic. This fusion of morality and epistemology risks circularity—what counts as true is what liberates, and what liberates is what is held to be true.

At the most antirealist/relativist end of the spectrum, Walter Mignolo [31] and Maria Lugones [32,33] move beyond the claim that power shapes or conditions knowledge to the view that there is no single reality to know. Each community, they argue, inhabits its own world with its own truths, so that the task is not to seek universality. For Mignolo, this takes the form of a “pluriverse” of equally valid knowledges; for Lugones, a multiplicity of lived worlds that resist assimilation into a single frame. It is through this recognition that power is to be redistributed. Epistemology is recast as an ethical and political exercise. Whether or not this is their intent, the consequence—remarkably aligned with Fricker—is a view that treats knowing as a moral relation among worlds rather than as an inquiry into what is true about the world. What begins as a critique of power ultimately evolves into ontological pluralism. The very idea of truth is displaced by the moral demand that many truths be recognised.

Defenders will insist that ‘pluriverse’ names a political-epistemic critique of modernity’s monopolisation of truth rather than a literal many-worlds ontology. However, that generous reading cannot easily be maintained. The very grammar of the claim—of distinct, incommensurable “worlds”—renders the slide into ontological relativism almost unavoidable. Once epistemic pluralism is expressed in ontological terms, the notion of a shared reality on which scientific inquiry depends is quietly abandoned. Indeed, this slippage is not merely theoretical; it is observable in the way the language of the pluriverse is deployed across the applied literature, where the rhetorical register routinely shifts from calls for epistemic inclusion to assertions of multiple, equally real worlds.

This progression—from realist accounts that treat truth as independent of power to pluralist accounts that dissolve truth into power—frames the intellectual background to the “decolonising” rhetoric now common in global health, where moral concern has come to stand in for epistemic warrant.

Few scholars within global health have attempted to develop a theoretical framework for decolonisation, and most draw on the work of others. Seye Abimbola stands out as one who explicitly draws on notions of epistemic injustice and “the foreign gaze” to theorise the relationship between (neo)colonialism and knowledge [6,22]. He develops a rich moral language in which unjust distributions of power are extended into the domain of knowledge itself. As a consequence, an irreducible tension arises between standpoint and truth. Indeed, Abimbola with his co-authors often fall into what I would describe as a conceptual mud-zone where in methodology they will fall on critical realist approaches (of Ray Pawson [34] and Nicholas Tilley [35], Margaret Archer [36], and Roy Bhaskar [37]) and conceptually step away from the realist commitment entailed by those methods [38]. Abimbola offers an interpretation that uses a methodologically realist account to adopt a more constructivist or antirealist position.

Knowledge is treated as positional, relational, and power-laden, rather than as an approximation of an underlying reality that we all share—appreciated or not. Truth is displaced by recognition—what matters is whose knowledge counts, not which claim best fits the evidence. Abimbola’s framework merges epistemology and ethics, making justice a criterion of truth.

Many other global health scholars draw either directly on decolonial theorists or indirectly through others who have done so, producing a spectrum of positions from realist to antirealist. This epistemological variation is particularly striking, since practitioners and researchers who are not writing about “decolonising” typically position themselves—explicitly or implicitly—within a realist framework. As will be seen, even some who write from an explicitly antirealist stance contort their arguments to yield a realist interpretation. A good example of this is a realist evaluation by Dimitri Renmans and colleagues [39].

Methodologically, the paper anchors itself in scientific realism. It affirms an independent reality, generative mechanisms, and the C(ontext)-M(echanisms)-O(utcome) logic of Pawson and Tilley [35]. Mechanisms in Pawson’s and Tilley’s framing are universal and capital-R, Real. It is the context, which may include aspects of power, that determines whether mechanisms are activated—causing a particular outcome.

Conceptually, however, they hybridise this realist frame within a decolonial and emancipatory ethic. They urge evaluators to treat local, incommensurate ontologies as “equivalent”. This idea of ontological equivalence is distinctly different from arguing that power can determine outcomes. The result is scientifically incoherent—a theoretically realist machinery deployed to sustain an antirealist ethic.

Authors such as Tiffany Nassiri-Ansari and Emma Rhule are far more straightforwardly antirealist, making no attempt to fall back on realist methodologies and drawing their intellectual lineage directly from Lugones and Mignolo [40,41]. They treat coloniality as a structural determinant of knowledge, not merely a contextual influence, and explicitly reject universality in favour of multiple “ways of knowing.” Here, a “way of knowing” is not understood as a different methodological route to insights about an underlying Real world but as an acceptance of multiple ontologies. The argument carries with it the moral clarity of almost all arguments for decolonisation, but weaves the epistemic confusion. Their project avoids the decolonial hybridisation of Renmans. However, it does dissolve the distinction between truth and perspective.

At the far end of the spectrum would be antirealist, relativist authors like Mohamad Al-Chami and colleagues [42]. They completely reject the idea of an underlying reality, and call for the dismantling of current knowledge and practices, and the promotion of “counter forms of knowledge and actions that construct another reality relevant to Indigenous world-views” (p. 5). Bound within a critique of power and the recognition of the enormous harms that indigenous groups have suffered is the interlaced, many-worlds view of reality.

A recurring tension within antirealist decolonial work is the attempt to preserve universal normative commitments whilst rejecting the epistemic universalism required to pursue them. The tension is visible to varying degrees across multiple contributions. Renmans and colleagues employ a realist methodology to sustain antirealist ethics, thereby creating methodological incoherence [38].

Nassiri-Ansari and Rhule reject universality in favour of multiple ways of knowing, yet their emancipatory project implicitly appeals to shared standards of justice [40,41]. The tension reaches its starkest form in recent work by Nadia Tagoe, Abimbola, and colleagues [43]. They invoke epistemic injustice to condemn structural inequity, endorse multiple epistemologies as a response, yet simultaneously call for agreement on universal health goals for practice—“health for all”. The position is philosophically unstable. If there is no shared reality and no universal standard of truth,

there can be no universal measure by which “better health” is judged or “health for all” is coordinated. The framework dissolves truth into perspectives whilst retaining a universal good that presupposes precisely what has been rejected. The dissonance goes beyond an abstract philosophical problem. Global health practice requires agreement on what works—on which interventions reduce mortality, prevent disease, or improve wellbeing. What works may change from place to place, because context matters. Nonetheless, without shared epistemic standards, such agreement becomes impossible, and “health for all” becomes an empty slogan rather than an achievable goal.

These antirealist approaches to the decolonisation of global health stand in marked contrast to authors such as David McCoy and Rajat Khosla [44,45] who frame the issue in structural terms. They describe “hierarchies in knowledge production” as manifestations of colonialism, linking them to the extraction, exploitation, and control of “intangible resources such as data and knowledge” [45]. They focus attention on “who leads”, “who controls”, and “who benefits”. [44] Their position is realist, grounded in historical materialism. Unfairness is portrayed as a continuation of colonial resource capture, visible in the “misappropriation of local knowledge and traditional remedies”. They observe unfairness perpetuated through parachute research, skewed authorship, biased grant systems, and epistemic hierarchies that privilege Northern institutions [44].

The critique is coherent. The surprise, however, is that McCoy and Khosla frame it through decolonisation. It is superfluous and limits the scope of their argument. At its core, they have identified structural unfairness with deep historical roots—an analysis of power. However, by attributing inequity solely to coloniality, they overlook the more fundamental nature of power that operates in all high-, low-, and middle-income countries, regardless of whether colonial histories are involved. Power ensures that the resources for knowledge creation, the accolades that attach to knowledge creation, the questions that are asked, and the policies and practices that evolve from them all filter to the advantage of particular groups. Power determines who benefits and how. The power differentials can be determined by factors such as ethnic group, geography, religion, socio-economic status, and others. The impacts can be within countries and between countries—even within and between countries in the Global South. Being from the Global South is no protection against being colonial in approach to others, treating indigenous groups as “less than”, dismissing people as ignorant or worthless based on a physical or social characteristic. All these things predated the European expansion of power—and as Europe has ceded power, others have been quick to fill the vacuum. Realigning the impact of history does not dismiss inequity or make it less valuable to understand and address. It does, however, correctly locate the thing to study.

Others go further, arguing that decolonisation discourse poses not merely analytical limits but active epistemic threats. In this regard, Hellowell and Schwerdtle stand apart [46]. They do not question that colonialism is unjust, but they do think that the injustice should not be treated as an argument for rejecting the universality of scientific reason. They reject the pluralist claim that different communities inhabit distinct epistemic worlds. For them, the conflation of moral standing with epistemic warrant undermines justified confidence in scientific knowledge. It replaces global solidarity with identity-based antagonism. They view relativism as a corrosive force, eroding the very possibility of global health as a unified enterprise.

Conclusion

The present vogue for epistemic injustice and decolonisation often trades on a category mistake. It converts moral standing into epistemic warrant. Those on the political left deployed this error, arguing that positionality confers authority. Those on the political right now deploy the same idea. Their sophistry lies in the valorisation of “our” community truths and suspicion of science. Both moves retreat from universal rights and from a shared, real world. They divide us into disconnected communities with no moral or epistemic basis for shared existence.

Nothing in this observation absolves global health of the manifest power failures that have arisen and been reinforced in its name. The structural critique of McCoy and Khosla remains: who decides, who leads, who owns the data, who is paid, who is credited, whose questions get asked—these remain urgent. Nevertheless, coloniality is only one lineage of power among many leading to these structural failures. A wider lens—poverty, class, religion, ethnicity, state capacity, professional cartels, philanthro-capitalism, and South–South hierarchies—does better explanatory work and avoids the parochialism of treating “colonial” as the master key [23].

It is perfectly reasonable to expect that scientific inquiry will draw on particular communities’ ways of conceiving the world [47]. This narrowing of the lens is, however, very different from claiming that all ontologies are equally valid. Science is not teleological—it does not proceed toward a predetermined end. It advances through diverse ways of theorising the world that, when tested, extend our shared understanding of reality.

The value of plural perspectives lies in their creative potential. It does not lie in the assertion that every idea has equal merit. The proper moral stance is epistemic humility, not relativism. It recognises that all knowledge is partial and situated, that inquiry is fallible and corrigible, and that truth nonetheless remains independent of us. Justice in global health, therefore, lies in ensuring that everyone has fair access to the benefits of knowledge and information. It does not lie in granting every claim equal authority.

One of the great ironies of the calls for epistemic justice and the decolonisation of global health is that much of it is performative [48]. The arguments are constructed, rationalised, and expressed in the manner required by the epistemic traditions of the Global North [11]. They convey their message through the very conduits of Northern epistemic power—the peer-reviewed journal article. Perhaps most egregiously, they sometimes sit behind paywalls that limit and control who is allowed access to the knowledge and who is allowed to be a part of the community of knowledge.

The difficulty is most apparent when one recognises that there is never a single “knower” but many, often in conflict. The example of snakebite makes the point. Across cultures, many “knowers” have advanced contrary beliefs about its treatment, sometimes causing grave harm to the patient [16]. Another example is found in the knowledge of traditional birth attendants and the management of postpartum haemorrhage, where excessive, life-threatening bleeding is treated as a natural cleansing of the body [49]. They cannot all be right, and when they are wrong, patients’ lives are put at risk. To treat every claim as equally credible is to abolish the idea of knowledge itself. Deciding which view is warranted requires standards of evidence external to their competing traditions. Justice in global health cannot rest on the equal recognition of knowers. For researchers, it lies in fair access

to the means of inquiry by which truth is determined. For those whom global health ultimately serves, it lies in fair access to the most effective, empirically warranted interventions.

A just global health does not need new shibboleths of virtue. It needs epistemic humility and disciplined attention to the interests of the populations being served. Its legitimacy rests on reciprocity, evidence, and equitable access to the means of inquiry. Knowledge should be tested by standards proportionate to the harm of error, and the capacity to undertake that testing should be broadly shared. The task is not to equalise every claim, but to ensure that inquiry proceeds where it matters most, and that those affected have a genuine part in shaping and using the results. Justice in this sense is procedural and practical. Research is led from context, benefits are shared transparently, and authority is aligned with competence. Under those conditions, science can remain realist without being parochial, and humane without abandoning truth.

The redistribution of global power is essential for achieving global health. It is a condition for realising the right to health, for achieving “health for all”, and for leaving no one behind. Tragically, the well-meaning calls for “epistemic justice” and for “decolonising global health” weaken both the moral and the epistemic foundations of that enterprise.

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